

CHANGE OF NOUN GROUPS IN PERSIAN LANGUAGE IN SPOKEN SPEECH

Ahmedova D.

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, DSc, Lecturer

Karimova M.

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, student

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Annotation: In this article, the phonetic features and their brief analysis are presented in the field of oral speech of the language, which are considered important and relevant for today, in the framework of noun word groups in Persian, and the author of the article expressed his thoughts and opinions.

Our object of research is also devoted to the study of phono-morphological features of speech elements within the verb phrase. For speakers of Persian language, in addition to the literary language, the language based on the Tehran dialect is also the norm for oral speech. But scientists have different opinions on this issue. Therefore, in the course of this research, it is the goal of the research to inform our opinions and conclusions by studying the opinions of scientists and analyzing examples collected from original sources. It is also important to analyze some phonetic changes that occur within the verb phrase in the Tehran dialect.

Key words: Noun, adjective, number, pronoun, Tehran dialect, regressive assimilation, oral speech, phonetic changes, long vowel, short vowel, nasal sound, phoneme, diphthong.

Spoken Persian is the spoken language of Iranians. In other words, Persian is the standard or official language. One is Persian, which is used for written speech, i.e. letters and official correspondence. The other is the formal spoken form of spoken Persian that learners and speakers can always converse with and enjoy. This form of oral speech is common in Tehran and other cities.

I. Phonetic (شکسته) changes occurring within the noun group.

1. If the long vowel o -â comes before the nasal sounds n-n and m-m, then the long vowel becomes u-w.

Animal - [حیوان] - animal

[خانه] - خاند - house

But this change above (o-â → u-w) is not always appropriate and is not common to all such words. For example, this phenomenon does not occur in the following words: slam, banag, pakstan

2. The vowel phoneme e-ai narrows significantly when it comes before the consonants ш-ш, н-н, ж-ж and ч-ч and is pronounced close to the phoneme ий- чозик.

[نیش] - نتش - grass, fire, fire

тёрт - [тёржарт] - trade

If the author of a work of fiction wants to reveal the character's speech, this change can be reflected in the written speech.

3. As a result of regressive assimilation, when consonant letters such as стст-, штшт-, зд-зд, фт-фт are side by side, the consonants т-т and д-д are lost in pronunciation.

dst - [ds] - arm

[مش] – مشت – fist

kft – [kf] – palm

dzd – [dz] – thief

If the author of a work of fiction wants to reveal the character's speech, this change can be reflected in the written speech.

4. In most cases, the throat consonant "hoye havvaz" - " h " -h at the end of the word is not pronounced.

kłah – [kłā] – cap, headdress

5. The voiced consonant j-zh is pronounced like the sliding consonants dj-zh or sh-sh in the composition of some words in the Tehran dialect.

[اشتماع] - اجتماع - to collect, collect.

II. Phonetic (श्रुत्य) changes that occur within the adjective word group.

1. If the long o-â vowel precedes the nasal sounds n-n and m-m, the long vowel becomes u-w.

mhrbān – [mhrbwn] – kind

2. The vowel phoneme e-ai narrows significantly when it comes before the consonants ш-ш, н-н, ж-ж and ч-ч and is pronounced close to the long phoneme и-й.

зшт – [зшт] - ugly

If the author of a work of art wants to reveal the idea in the character's speech, this change can also be reflected in the written speech.

3. When the consonants n-n and d-d come together at the end of the word, the consonant d-d is lost in pronunciation.

blnd – [bln] – tall

III. Phonetic شکسته changes that occur within the number of words.

1. The vowel phoneme e-ai narrows significantly when it comes before the consonants ш-ш, н-н, ж-ж and ч-ч and is pronounced close to the long phoneme и-й.

[شیش] – شش – six

hjd h – [هیزده] – eighteen

If the author of a work of fiction wants to reveal the character's speech, this change can be reflected in the written speech.

2. At the end of the word, when consonant letters such as ст-ст, шт-шт, фт-фт come side by side, the consonant т-т is not pronounced.

[بیست] – بیست – twenty

[هشت] – هشت – eight

hft – [hf] – seven

3. "Hoye havvaz" - the consonant phoneme " h " -h is often dropped when it comes between two vowel phonemes and when it comes after a vowel phoneme at the end of the word.

چهل – [چل] – forty

4. In the series of words, the consonant at the end of the word "yḵ" is dropped in pronunciation.

yḵ – [yh] – one

5. The voiced consonant j-zh is pronounced like the sliding consonants dj-zh or sh-sh in the composition of some words in the Tehran dialect.

hjd h – [هیزده] – eighteen

IV. Phonetic شکسته changes that occur within the pronoun word group.

1. If the long o-â vowel precedes the nasal sounds n-n and m-m, the long vowel becomes u-w.

ân - [awn] -u (for objects)

2. The second vowel in the o'u-w diphthong, i.e. u-w, is not pronounced in the Tehran dialect. As a result of rapid pronunciation, the diphthong o'u-w turns into o-au.

چطور؟ - [چطر؟] - how?

3. When the consonants n-n and d-d come together at the end of the word, the consonant d-d is lost in pronunciation.

why? - [чн?] - how much?

4. In the series of words, the consonant at the end of the following word is dropped in pronunciation.

هیچ چیز - [هیچ چی] - nothing

5. The voiceless ч-ч consonant loses its explosive character in the Tehran dialect and is pronounced as ш-ш.

کس هیث - [کس هیش] - nobody

Conclusion

We have analyzed the above-mentioned changes of شکسته that occur in the oral speech of the Persian language and have reached the standard level by analyzing the examples taken from video, audio and internet books. These six changes are not appropriate for all words, for example, when Iranians themselves change proper nouns during communication, that is, people's names, names of states and cities, these changes are not considered normal. Also, there are some words in the Tehran dialect, which is the dialect of the residents of Tehran, the capital of Iran.

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